

TO‘RT QAHRAMON VA TO‘RTTA YO‘L

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada barchaning sevimli yozuvchisi Tohir Malikning “Chorrahada qolgan odamlar”, ya’ni “Devona” asarining tahlili keltirilgan. “Devona” fantastik qissa bo‘lib, uning chorrahada qolgan to‘rt qahramonning hayoti hikoya qilinadi. Maqolada ushbu qahramonlarning xarakteri, asarda tutgan o‘rni tahlil qilingan.

ЧЕТЫРЕ ГЕРОЯ И ЧЕТЫРЕ ДОРОГИ

Аннотация

В данной статье представлен анализ всеми любимого писателя Тахира Малика “Люди на распутье”, он же “Безумный”. “Сумасшедший” – это фэнтезийная история, повествующая о жизни четырех персонажей, оказавшихся на распутье. В статье анализируется характер этих героев, их роль в произведении.

FOUR HEROES AND FOUR ROADS

Annotation

This article presents an analysis of everyone's favorite writer, Tahir Malik's "People at the Crossroads," aka "Mad." "Crazy" is a fantasy story, which tells the lives of four characters who find themselves at a crossroads. The character of these heroes, their role in the work is analyzed in the article.

Kalit so‘zlar: fantastik qissa, qahramon, xarakter, chorrahada qolganlar, mavzu, g‘oya, ruhiyat tahlili, tarbiya, ziddiyat, odob, detektiv asarlar, ma’rifiy asarlar.

Ключевые слова: художественный рассказ, герой, персонаж, перепутье, тема, идея, психологический анализ, воспитание, конфликт, манеры, детективные произведения, воспитательные произведения.

Key words: fictional story, hero, character, crossroads, theme, idea, psychological analysis, education, conflict, manners, detective works, educational works.

The world of literature is extremely colorful, artistic creation is a mysterious and magical phenomenon that does not recognize ready-made templates. Literature in a broad sense can be understood as follows: "Manners include politeness, delicacy, good manners, good manners and good behavior with others. Taking these meanings into account, the word "adab" was derived from the archaic word "literature" in the

form of "literature" and made it a term for stories, poems, short stories, and parables. Because these are things that give education, delicacy and beauty to people's nature, thoughts and feelings. By the word "literature" in its broadest sense, we understand all the thoughts and concepts, feelings and imaginations that are spoken or written in an orderly manner" [3].

Tahir Malik's work brought new directions to Uzbek literature with his fantastic, detective and educational works. He is one of the creators who has a unique status in literature. Studying his work makes it possible to clarify very important issues of contemporary literature. There are many aspects of the writer's legacy that need special research. The number of published works is also high.

In the works of fiction, the role of the creator of miracles is performed by fantastic images. In T. Malik's short story "People at the Crossroads", biotok flows serve as an illustration. Rhaq, one of the main characters of the work, descends from Tang planet to Earth through biotok currents, gets acquainted with the life of earthlings. Rhaq also works on earth like earthlings. There are supernatural circumstances in the story that the writer can convince the reader. Rhaq is troubled by only one thing - the existence of two opposing types of life on two planets. He is envied in the life of earthlings. The sense of understanding a person and his heart is alien to the people of Tang. Most importantly, they lack human affection. Rhaq is a person who is in a state of apostasy. The reason is that he cannot leave his country, and at the same time, the life of the locals attracts him. The skill of the writer is that he penetrates the world of Rhaqrshi based on the comparison of the people of the two planets. Thus, the character of the writer's hero is clarified through the flow of a fantastic description - biotok.

As we know, the image of extraterrestrials and aliens occupies the main place in a fantastic work. Writers skillfully used both realistic and fantastic methods of expression to portray them. Writer Tahir Malik in the story "People at the Crossroads" draws the image of Lukn, who visited Earth from Tang planet, as follows: "This man is tall, broad-shouldered, with fire in his eyes..." [1]. Tahir Malik's portraits are concise and clear. He pays attention to the most important points in the appearance of his character. YA describes the aliens as similar to the natives. The portraits created by Tahir Malik also have an inhumanity, but it is presented in a hidden state.

The presentation of the mental and psychological images of Rhaq and Sabohiddin in the work "People left at the crossroads" confirms our opinion. Rhaq burns in pain and suffering as he observes the fiery life on earth. The reason is that what surprised him on Earth does not exist on his planet. Tang was stunned. Even human death does not

bother them. Rhaq is distressed by this situation: "Tomorrow the baby will be buried, but no one will mourn for this child. That is the value of a creature. On the ground, it is completely different. People even agree to follow the deceased into the grave. Maybe it's an oversimplification, but it's still good to burn. Rhaq leaned on a soft low chair and remembered the earthlings" [1].

When Rhaq compares this situation on Earth and in Tang, selfless and humble people on earth come to mind. Tahir Malik's works are rich in lyricism, in which poetic expression prevails. The person he trusts will pull his brother's head to Sabohiddin. This episode in the work is noteworthy and impressive: "The mountains were also frozen. The sky too. The soul has drained from the veins of the world. It happened for a moment, just for a moment. He dropped the head in his hand. His brother's severed head fell into the snow. A cry from Sabahiddi's heart broke the silence. The mountains echoed. No, it's not sound. The mountains cried out.

The snow could not contain this cry, it absorbed it into the bosom of the sky" [1]. This passage can be called a prose poem, so to speak. Sabohiddin reaches into his bag for food and grabs something cold. That cold thing was his brother's head. The writer connects Sabohiddi's sufferings at this moment with situations in nature. The earth, the sky, the mountains - the whole existence was a witness of this horror, it seems. The writer masterfully used animation. The cry of the mountains, freezing, life coming out of the blood vessels of the world - revitalization, human characteristics are transferred to nature. These horrors happened in front of the eyes of Sabahiddin, who was completely covered by darkness, and made him go crazy. T. Malik entered the spiritual world of his heroes in these ways [4]. In other words, he is an artist of the psyche. Analyzing this work, M. Mahmudov emphasizes that the writer has a deep understanding of the breadth of the human psyche, that the story includes the material of a novel, and calls it the first Uzbek fantasy novel [1].

Tahir Malik perfected the direction of detective fiction and managed to reveal the subtle aspects of the characters' mental world. In it, imagination and reality collided [4].

Tahir Malik's "People at the Crossroads" has both a fantastical and a realistic spirit. The character of Rhaq in the work is formed as a fantastic character. Sabahiddin is a realistic character. This image embodies the important aspects of nationalism. Sabohiddin was brought up in the East from a young age, received a madrasa education, and knows Uzbek traditions well. The most important thing is faith. At the same time, he is a child of complicated times. Even the complexities of the time could

not bend his faith. This character reflects the Uzbek worldview, the tragedy of the people in the dark years. Sabohiddin has the following characteristics: this character is a product of reality; It contains Uzbek characteristics and has acquired the essence of typicality; the complexities of the period had an impact on the unfolding of the nature of the character; Uzbek tragedy lies at the basis of their suffering; It shows the image of the people of the 1930s, that is, the image of Uzbeks who have remained in the wilderness.

In general, Tahir Malik tries to illuminate all aspects of the complex human character [4].

Tahir Malik's work brought new directions to Uzbek literature with his fantastic, detective and educational works. He is one of the creators who has a unique status in literature. Studying his work makes it possible to clarify very important issues of contemporary literature. There are many aspects of the writer's legacy that need special research. The number of published works is also high.

Tahir Malik also re-edited the novel "Standing at the Crossroads" and changed some parts. Little attention is paid to the mental state of the heroes. These places were corrected and the pages that were not allowed by the censor were rewritten and the original title of the work – "Mad" was restored.

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